

Cooperation between the states of the Turkic Commonwealth and the Republic of Uzbekistan

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Abstract: In the article, it is stated that in the 21st century of globalization, increasing the role and significance of the principle of tolerance in the fate of the current world, and rising to the level of an incredibly unique cultural event and phenomenon in the life of society. It is emphasized that the Central Asian region is increasingly gaining its place in the world community and participates in socio-political and economic processes on an equal basis. In the article, it is proved that the representatives of indigenous peoples of the Central Asian region have been living side by side with the peoples of other nationalities and religions since ancient times, and tolerance among the peoples has become not only a need created by necessity, but a way of life.

Key words: Central Asia, foreign policy, public diplomacy, interethnic harmony, tolerance, friendship societies, national cultural centers.

Central Asia has an incredible history of interethnic harmony. The Silk Road, in addition to forming a network of trade routes, enabled the spread of ideas and beliefs along the way. Various communities interacted and coexisted over long periods of time illustrating how different beliefs and civilizations can exist side by side with respect and tolerance. For thousands of years, Central Asia has become a space where representatives of incredibly diverse nationalities and religions lived in peace, where world civilization and cultures of different peoples enriched each other. Original human values, such as hospitality, tolerance, expansiveness, towards representatives of other nationalities and religions, which have become an integral

part of our lifestyle, have also found their bright expression in the invaluable legacy left by the greatness of the Uzbek, Tajik, Turkmen, Kyrgyz and Kazakh nationalities living in our region. Therefore, ensuring interethnic harmony and solidarity in the society, strengthening interconfessional dialogue, as well as developing friendly relations with foreign countries became one of the priorities of the state policy of independent Uzbekistan.

From the first days of independence, special attention was paid to strengthening inter-ethnic harmony as an important factor in ensuring peace and prosperity, and legal foundations were created to ensure equal rights and freedom of more than 130 nationalities belonging to 16 religious denominations living in Uzbekistan. Maintaining and strengthening the atmosphere of harmony, mutual respect and kindness of the nations and citizens that prevail in our country is a priority in the speech of Shavkat Mirziyoyev on the solemn ceremony of entering the post of President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. As a result of the study and analysis of foreign experience in the field of legal regulation of interethnic relations, more than 40 regulatory legal Acts-2 laws, 9 decrees and 8 decisions of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 20 decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers, 3 decisions of the Supreme Assembly were adopted in the years of independence.

In particular, the important issue of ensuring interethnic harmony and tolerance during the creation of a new history of Uzbekistan, expanding cultural and educational ties with foreign countries was identified as a strategy of action on the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan and a special direction in the development strategy of new Uzbekistan. The Committee on interethnic relations and friendly cooperation with foreign countries under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, established in 2017, in

cooperation with 152 national cultural centers, 38 Friendly Societies and 38 compatriots abroad, contributes significantly to ensuring interethnic and interreligious harmony in society, promoting friendly relations and cultural and educational relations with foreign countries, establishing close relations with compatriots abroad[8]. Due to the political will of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, border points of Uzbekistan were opened with neighboring countries. As a result of Uzbekistan's open, friendly and practical foreign policy, in the following years, completely new political, economic and cultural relations were established between the countries of Central Asia. In the past five years Uzbekistan has taken concrete steps reaching out to its immediate neighbours and continues to promote improved relations. This has had a concrete impact on the lives of people in Central Asia who can now visit their relatives across borders with more ease. All countries in the region have much to gain from good neighborly relations and increased connectivity. Just recently on 11 July the UN General Assembly passed a resolution initiated by Uzbekistan on Strengthening connectivity between Central and South Asia. In addition to trade and transport, infrastructure, logistics and shipping, the new resolution also highlights the importance of regional connectivity in building and sustaining peace, stability, and security in the region. Regional cooperation is an effective form of multilateralism and international cooperation contributing to the promotion of the purposes and principles of the United Nations, including accelerating the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals. As the world is in turmoil and facing multiple interconnected challenges such as climate change, the continuing covid-19 pandemic, food security, conflict. We can only solve these challenges through regional and global cooperation. It is of utmost importance that cooperation and friendship remain at the top of the agenda by promoting tolerance, respect, and mutual understanding to achieve peaceful, just and inclusive societies.

Also, a clear example of this is the sharp increase in the number of bilateral dialogues between the heads of states of our region in recent years. In particular, the establishment of the practice of regular holding of consultative meetings of the heads of Central Asian states according to the initiative put forward by the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly in September 2017 brought cooperation to a completely new level.

Thanks to consultation meetings, we managed to strengthen friendship and good neighborly relations, create a completely new atmosphere of constructive cooperation in our region. As a result of the acceptance of Uzbekistan as a full member of the Turkic Council on September 15, 2019, within the framework of the organization, not only cultural and spiritual ties, but also trade and economic relations are reaching a new level. Based on the decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the establishment of the people's diplomacy center of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization in Uzbekistan on June 26, 2018 promotes the strengthening of mutual trust and good neighborliness, interethnic and interreligious harmony between the member countries of the organization, strengthening intercivilizational dialogue.

In order to conduct scientific research aimed at studying the diversity of cultures and traditions and the modern processes of sustainable development of the countries of the region, the International Institute of Central Asia, established in Tashkent in August 2020, contributes to the comprehensive expansion of cooperation between neighboring countries.

By decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan on November 15, 2019, the adoption of the state policy concept of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of interethnic relations laid the groundwork for the radical improvement of interethnic relations and friendship relations with foreign countries.

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